

CATALYTIC CONVERSION OF D-GLUCOSE INTO SORBITOL AND GLUCONIC ACID**Natigə Suleymanli***Baku Engineering university***Ə.R.Sucayev***k.e.d., dosent**Academician A.M.Guliyev Institute of Chemistry of Additives***Y.Ə.Abdullayev***k.e.d., dosent**Baku Engineering university***Abstract**

The catalytic oxidation of D-glucose into sorbitol and gluconic acid is a significant biochemical process that has both industrial relevance and implications for metabolic pathways. This article explores the mechanisms, types of catalysts, and conditions that promote this transformation, offering insights to enhance yield and efficiency. D-glucose is a multifunctional monosaccharide that is crucial in numerous biochemical and industrial functions. Two key derivatives of D-glucose, sorbitol and gluconic acid, find extensive application in the food, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and industrial sectors. Sorbitol serves as a sugar alcohol utilized for its sweetness and moisture-retaining properties, while gluconic acid acts as a vital intermediate in chemical synthesis and is a precursor for producing a range of valuable chemicals. The transformation of D-glucose into sorbitol and gluconic acid entails various catalytic processes, with multiple catalyst types (homogeneous, heterogeneous, and biocatalysts) employed to attain elevated yields and specific product distributions. Each catalytic method presents distinct advantages and obstacles that are essential to address for optimizing these transformations in industrial contexts.

Keywords: D-glucose, Sorbitol, Gluconic acid, Catalysis, Good health and well-being, affordable and clean energy.

Introduction

D-glucose is a vital monosaccharide that acts as the main energy source in living organisms. The process of converting it into the sugar alcohol sorbitol and the organic acid gluconic acid is of considerable interest because of its uses in food, medicine, and biochemistry. This study aims to investigate the catalytic oxidation process that facilitates the transformation of D-glucose into these important products.

The catalytic oxidation of D-glucose represents an intriguing field of research, particularly due to its potential applications in generating sorbitol and gluconic acid. These substances hold significant value across numerous industries, including food, pharmaceuticals, and cosmetics.

Moreover, the mechanism of the reaction is intricate. The process begins with the oxidation of D-glucose, which produces intermediate compounds that can be transformed into either sorbitol or gluconic acid. Scientists are working to optimize these conditions to favor the production of one compound over the other.

In summary, grasping the complexities of this catalytic oxidation process is essential. With ongoing advancements in catalyst development and reaction optimization, producing sorbitol and gluconic acid from D-glucose could become more efficient and sustainable. Future research will surely provide further insights into this promising field of study.

- Sorbitol Production:

The transformation of D-glucose into sorbitol can take place through enzymatic pathways, mainly involving the enzyme aldose reductase. Nonetheless, this study concentrates on the catalytic oxidation process, which can also yield sorbitol under specific conditions.

- In this regard, employing metal catalysts can enhance the reduction of D-glucose to sorbitol, accelerating the reaction rate and improving yield.

- This hydrogenation process entails converting glucose by hydrogenating the aldehyde group to generate a sugar alcohol. Sorbitol is commonly utilized as a sugar alternative, humectant, and moisturizing agent in food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical products.

Catalysts employed in the glucose to sorbitol conversion include:

- ✓ Homogeneous Catalysts:

In homogeneous catalysis, the catalyst exists in the same phase as the reactants (typically in a solution). Metal-based catalysts are often utilized in this method:

- Nickel (Ni) and Platinum (Pt) Catalysts: These are the most frequently used catalysts for the hydrogenation of D-glucose to sorbitol. Nickel is commonly favored in industrial applications due to its relatively low price, whereas platinum catalysts, although more costly, offer high activity.

- Ruthenium (Ru) Catalysts: Ruthenium serves as another effective catalyst for glucose hydrogenation, providing high activity and selectivity, but its expense may limit its use for large-scale production.

Mechanism: The hydrogenation process involves adding hydrogen (H₂) across the C=O bond of glucose's aldehyde group, converting it into a hydroxyl group and resulting in sorbitol.

- ✓ Heterogeneous Catalysts:

Heterogeneous catalysts are often preferred in various industrial processes as they are simpler to separate from the reaction mixture and allow for catalyst recycling.

- Nickel (Ni) Supported on Inert Materials: Nickel-based catalysts supported on materials like alumina (Al_2O_3) or silica (SiO_2) are commonly utilized for glucose hydrogenation. These supports provide a high surface area and stability.

- Ruthenium and Palladium on Carbon (Ru/C, Pd/C): These catalysts are also applied in glucose hydrogenation, offering high selectivity and activity. The carbon support aids in dispersing the metal catalyst, which enhances its effectiveness.

The benefits of heterogeneous catalysis include improved catalyst separation and recycling; however, these reactions usually require higher pressures and temperatures compared to homogeneous catalysts. 3. Biocatalysts:

✓ Biocatalysis involves the use of enzymes to catalyze the conversion of glucose to sorbitol. This process is attractive because of its specificity, mild reaction conditions, and environmental sustainability.

Glucose Hydrogenase (GoxH): Certain microbial enzymes, like glucose hydrogenase derived from bacteria or fungi, have the ability to transform glucose into sorbitol. These enzymes are frequently utilized in biotechnological applications to generate The benefits of biocatalysis include gentle reaction conditions, the absence of toxic heavy metals, and a low environmental impact, although the catalytic efficiency may not always reach the levels of industrial hydrogenation processes.

- Gluconic Acid Production:

- The conversion of D-glucose to gluconic acid is facilitated by glucose oxidase, which predominantly utilizes molecular oxygen as the oxidizing agent. This reaction can be optimized through various catalysts, including transition metals and enzymes, to enhance the efficiency and selectivity in the production of gluconic acid.

Reaction environment for conversion of D-Glucose to Sorbitol

Sorbitol, a sugar alcohol, is extensively utilized as a low-calorie sweetener in both the food and pharmaceutical sectors. The process of converting D-glucose to sorbitol entails the reduction of the aldehyde group (-CHO) present in glucose to a primary alcohol group (-CH₂OH). This hydrogenation reaction is typically performed in the presence of hydrogen gas (H_2) along with an appropriate catalyst and can occur in either aqueous or non-aqueous environments.

Key Factors Influencing the Reaction:

- Temperature and Pressure: The reaction is generally conducted at elevated temperatures (usually between 100-150°C) and moderate pressures (3-6 MPa) to facilitate effective hydrogenation. While higher temperatures and pressures can enhance the reaction rate, they may also result in the generation of unwanted by-products.

- Solvent: This reaction is often performed in an aqueous environment, although non-aqueous solvents

like alcohols or ethers are also viable options. Water is commonly favored since it boosts the solubility of D-glucose, which is hydrophilic, and sorbitol is also highly soluble in water.

- Reaction Time: The conversion of D-glucose to sorbitol is a relatively slow reaction that usually requires several hours to attain significant conversion rates. The duration of the reaction can differ depending on the catalyst used and the operating conditions.

Reaction Mechanism:

1. The glucose molecule binds to the catalyst surface.

2. Hydrogen gas splits into atomic hydrogen, which then interacts with the aldehyde group of glucose.

3. The aldehyde group is transformed into a hydroxymethyl group, producing sorbitol.

Although the reaction is typically selective, yielding sorbitol as the primary product, some side reactions may take place, resulting in byproducts such as mannitol and other polyols.

- ❖ . Conversion of D-Glucose to Gluconic Acid

The conversion of D-glucose into gluconic acid is an essential process that has uses in the food industry and the manufacturing of specialty chemicals.

Important Factors Influencing the Reaction:

- Oxidizing Agents: The oxidation of D-glucose is usually achieved with mild oxidizing agents such as oxygen (O_2), bromine (Br_2), or through a combination of glucose and an enzyme like glucose oxidase (GOx). In industrial settings, oxygen is commonly used alongside a catalyst (for example, a copper-based catalyst) for large-scale oxidation processes.

- pH and Temperature: The oxidation of D-glucose is influenced by pH, with the optimal range being between 6.0 and 7.5. Elevated pH levels might lead to undesired side reactions and byproducts. While enzymatic oxidation typically occurs at temperatures between 30 and 50°C, chemical oxidation reactions are generally conducted at higher temperatures (ranging from 60 to 100°C) to accelerate the reaction.

- Solvent: The conversion of D-glucose into gluconic acid is generally performed in an aqueous solution to enhance the solubility of both glucose and the resultant product. Organic solvents are rarely utilized, as gluconic acid is highly soluble in water, and aqueous environments are more conducive for maintaining catalyst stability.

Reaction Mechanism:

1. The glucose molecule interacts with the oxidizing agent (either oxygen or the glucose oxidase enzyme).

2. The aldehyde functional group of glucose is converted into a carboxyl group (-COOH), leading to the production of gluconic acid.

3. In the enzymatic oxidation process, glucose oxidase facilitates the reaction using oxygen to oxidize glucose, resulting in the formation of hydrogen peroxide as a byproduct that may need to be neutralized or eliminated.

Summary

Catalyst Type	Sorbitol Production	Gluconic Acid Production
Common Homogeneous Catalysts that used for sorbitol and gluconic acid productions	Metal catalysts (Ni, Pt, Ru)	Oxidation with Cr, Mn, Cu-based catalysts
Heterogeneous Catalysts that used for sorbitol and gluconic acid productions	Metal-supported heterogen catalysts (Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ , Ru/C)	Metal oxides (MnO ₂ , Co ₃ O ₄), Pt, Pd, Ru-supported heterogen catalysts
Biocatalysts that used for sorbitol and gluconic acid productions	Enzymes such as glucose hydrogenase.	Glucose oxidase enzymes.(GOx)

3. Comparing the gluconic acid and sorbitol synthesis.

Aspect	Hydrogenation (Glucose to Sorbitol)	Oxidation (Glucose to Gluconic Acid)
Type of Reaction	Reduction (hydrogenation)	Oxidation
Catalysts	Nickel, platinum, palladium, ruthenium	Copper compounds, glucose oxidase
Reactants	Glucose and hydrogen gas	Glucose and oxidizing agents (O ₂ , Br ₂)
Conditions	High temperature, medium pressure	Mild temperature and pH conditions
Main Product	Sorbitol	Gluconic acid
By-products	Mannitol, other polyols	Side sugars, incomplete oxidation

Conclusion

The transformation of D-glucose into sorbitol and gluconic acid encompasses distinct reaction mechanisms that necessitate meticulous regulation of the reaction conditions. The incorporation of hydrogen gas along with metal catalysts is essential for the hydrogenation process, whereas oxidation reactions rely on the application of gentle oxidizing agents and particular pH levels. Grasping the significance of catalysts, solvents, temperature, and pressure is critical for enhancing these methods and ensuring the delivery of high-quality products for industrial applications. As the demand for both sorbitol and gluconic acid grows, continued research aimed at discovering more efficient and sustainable reaction conditions is vital to fulfill the requirements of the food, pharmaceutical, and chemical sectors.

Investigations into the catalytic oxidation of D-glucose to produce sorbitol and gluconic acid indicate considerable opportunities for refining manufacturing techniques in industrial contexts. By comprehending the catalytic processes and the effect of various influences, it becomes possible to boost the efficiency and

output of these important compounds. Future studies should prioritize the creation of more effective catalysts and the examination of alternative reaction pathways. The conversion of D-glucose to sorbitol and gluconic acid plays a crucial role in numerous industries. The selection of catalyst—whether homogeneous, heterogeneous, or biocatalytic—hinges on elements such as cost, efficiency, environmental implications, and scalability. Although homogeneous catalysts remain prevalent in sorbitol production, heterogeneous and biocatalytic methods are increasingly being adopted due to their sustainable features and reusability. For gluconic acid production, utilizing biocatalysis with glucose oxidase presents an encouraging, eco-friendly alternative, while metal-based catalysts continue to be frequently employed in industrial oxidation procedures.

References

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